

The Late Pliocene/Early Pleistocene marine mollusc deposit of Selemonachi, Kos (Greece).-

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Abstract

In Selemonachi, Kos (Greece), 55 different species of fossil molluscs from the Late Pliocene/Early Pleistocene were recovered. 46 of the 55 fossil mollusc species found are documented for Kos for the first time.

Zusammenfassung

In Selemonachi, Kos (Griechenland), wurden 55 verschiedene Arten von fossilen Mollusken aus dem Späten Pliozän/Frühen Pleistozän geborgen. 46 der 55 gefundenen fossilen Mollusken-Arten werden erstmals für Kos dokumentiert.

Introduction

In this article we present the rich mollusc fauna of a Late Pliocene/Early Pleistocene site in Kos (Greece), especially the site of Selemonachi. Little is known about the fossil marine mollusc fauna of the island. In this paper we will try to give a better understanding for the Late Pliocene/Early Pleistocene marine mollusc fauna of Kos. The only publication on marine fossil molluscs of this era on the island was written by WALTSCHEW 1997. He mainly reported on fossil Foraminifera and Ostracoda and it includes a short list of marine molluscs of the Tafi formation.

Fig. 1: Kos: Selemonachi site (blue point) between Mastichari and Antimacheia town (© google maps).

Fig. 2: General view of the locality.

Geological setting

The site is located between the towns of Antimacheia and Mastichari on Kos island (figs. 1, 2). It is situated 90 meters above sea level and consists of Early Pleistocene marine clays. There are two distinct layers in the section, one thin 10 mm clay layer with concretions and Turritellidae and a second 50 mm layer with rich marine deposits (figs. 3, 4, 6), which consists of brown clays and small sized conglomerates. Many features analyzed in the discussion part suggest Late Pliocene age for this site. WILLMANN 1983 made a geological map for central Kos, but did not name this formation. He also considers the site as a formation of Plio-Pleistocene age. We propose to introduce the name Selemonachi formation.

Methods

The large fossils like *Panopea faujasi* and the little but fragile ones like *Acanthocardia echinata* were extracted using a Rill super glue and after this quick preparation in the field we used a Paraloid b-72 10% solution to harden them. Most fossils were hand-picked from the weathered surface, while smaller fossils were gathered by washing the sediment through a 2 mm sieve.

Results

Table 1:

	1	2	
<i>Theodoxus doricus fontannesii</i> (NEUMAYR 1880)		x	
<i>Alvania</i> cf. <i>cimex</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Gibbula magus</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Steromphala adansonii</i> (PAYRAUDEAU 1826)		x	
<i>Calliostoma tauromiliare</i> (SACCO 1896)		x	fig. 10
<i>Bolma rugosa</i> (LINNAEUS 1767) + Opercula		x	fig. 11
<i>Bittium latreillii</i> (PAYRAUDEAU 1826)		x	
<i>Cerithium vulgatum</i> BRUGUIERE 1792		x	

<i>Melanopsis gorceixi broti</i> NEUMAYR 1880		x	
<i>Turritella communis</i> RISSO 1826	x ¹		
<i>Turritellinella tricarinata</i> (BROCCHI 1814)		x	
<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Vermetus deshayesi</i> (MAYER 1889)		x	
<i>Trivia arctica</i> (PULTENEY 1799)		x	fig. 10
<i>Naticarius punctatus</i> (KARSTEN 1789)	x ²		
<i>Naticarius stercusmuscarum</i> (GMELIN 1791)		x	
<i>Euspira catena</i> (DA COSTA 1778)		x	
<i>Neverita josephina</i> RISSO 1826 + Opercula	x	x	fig. 8
<i>Hadriana</i> sp.		x	
<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Tritia neritea</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	fig. 9
<i>Tritia nitida</i> (JEFFREYS 1867)		x	
<i>Nassarius angulatus</i> (BROCCHI 1814)		x	
<i>Nassarius companyoi</i> (FONTANNES 1879)		x	
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)	x ³		
<i>Nassarius striatulus</i> (EICHWALD 1829)		x	
<i>Columbella rustica</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Costoanachis</i> sp.		x	
<i>Euthria cornea</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Gracilipurpura rostrata</i> (OLIVI 1792)		x	fig. 12
<i>Fasciolaria lawleyana</i> (D' ANCONA 1872)		x	
<i>Vexillum</i> cf. <i>frumentum</i> (BELLARDI 1887)		x	
<i>Comarmondia gracilis</i> (MONTAGU 1803)		x	fig. 13
<i>Ringicula auriculata</i> (MENARD DE LA GROYE 1811)		x	
<i>Antalis dentalis</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Antalis inaequicostata</i> (DAUTZENBERG 1891)		x	
<i>Dischides politus</i> (S. WOOD 1842)		x	
<i>Nucula</i> cf. <i>jeffreysi</i> BELLARDI 1875		x	
<i>Nucula nitidosa</i> WINCKWORTH 1930		x	
<i>Saccella commutata</i> (PHILIPPI 1844)		x	
<i>Anadara demiri</i> (PIANI 1981)	x ⁴		
<i>Anadara diluvii</i> (LAMARCK 1805)		x	
<i>Glycimeris insubrica</i> (BROCCHI 1814)			
<i>Mytilus</i> cf. <i>edulis</i> LINNAEUS 1758	x	x	
<i>Pecten jacobaeus</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)	x	x	
<i>Chlamys glabra</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)	x ⁵		
<i>Chlamys varia</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)	x ⁶		
<i>Anomia ephippium</i> LINNAEUS 1758	x		
<i>Ostrea edulis</i> LINNAEUS 1758	x	x	
<i>Magallana angulata</i> (LAMARCK 1819)	x ⁷	x	
<i>Chama gryphoides</i> LINNAEUS 1758		x	
<i>Chama placentina</i> (DEFRANCE 1817)		x	fig. 14
<i>Acanthocardia spinosa</i> (LIGHTFOOT 1786)		x	
<i>Acanthocardia echinata</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Acanthocardia paucicostata</i> (G. B. SOWERBY II 1834)	x		
<i>Procardium diluvianum</i> (LAMARCK 1819)		x	
<i>Laevicardium oblongum</i> (GMELIN 1791)		x	

<i>Spondylus gaederopus</i> LINNAEUS 1758		x	
<i>Cerastoderma edule</i> LINNAEUS 1758		x	
<i>Spisula subtruncata</i> (DA COSTA 1778)		x	
<i>Clausinella fasciata</i> (DA COSTA 1778)		x	fig. 7
<i>Callista chione</i> (LINNAEUS 1758)		x	
<i>Varicorbula gibba</i> (OLIVI 1792)		x	
<i>Panopea faujasi</i> MENARD DE LA GROYE 1807		x	

1 = Tafi Formation (WALTSCHW 1997) (14 fossil species + 9 recent species).

2 = new location (55 species).

Remarks

x¹- still identified as *Turritella communis* by WALTSCHW 1997. The valid name is *Turritellinella tricarinata*.

x²- as *Naticarius punctatus* - synonym of *Naticarius stercusmuscarum*.

x³ - *Nassarius reticulatus* - synonym of *Tritia reticulata*, distribution: European Atlantic coast, the fossil Nassariidae from Kos is *Tritia nitida* as well as the recent ones.

x⁴- WALTSCHW 1997 lists an *Anadara demiri* as species. However, this is a synonym of *Anadara transversa* (SAY 1822). This bivalve, originally native to America, was first recorded in the Mediterranean in 1972. Therefore this species cannot originate from the Pliocene of Kos. In our meaning, this is *Anadara diluvii*.

x⁵- = *Flexopecten glaber*.

x⁶ - = *Mimachlamys varia*.

x⁷- as *Crassostrea angulata* in the list of WALTSCHW 1997 is now placed in the genus *Magallana*.

Discussion

Among the mollusks there were *Cladocora caespitosa* LINNAEUS 1758-remains and urchin fragments of *Brissus unicolor* (LESKE 1778). DRINIA & al. 2010 describe a similar site from Kos. During a first phase 55 species (tab. 1) of molluscs could be found and some of them can be used to determine the age of the formation. A fragmented *Procardium diluvianum* (LAMARCK 1819) is the first record for Kos. This species is known from several sites in Italy, France and Rhodes (Greece). There are two recent publications on a Pliocene site of Harokopio (SW-Peloponnese, Greece) with great similarities with the fossil mollusc fauna of Kos (SCHNEIDER & HOCHLEITNER 2006, KOSKERIDOU & al. 2017), all assuming Pliocene age. A complete specimen of *Acanthocardia echinata* was found. This specimen was the type with spoon shaped spines. Following LA PERNA & D'ABRAMO 2011 records of this form lived in Italy from Early-Middle Pliocene and through the Pleistocene. Many *Panopea* specimens were seen, all of them in natural position and 2 complete specimens were extracted. We think that it is *Panopea faujasi* (fig. 5), like those found on the near island of Rhodes suggesting it also of Pliocene age (THOMSEN & al. 2009).

Paleoecological considerations

The presence of these molluscs, echinoderms and corals suggests a shallow water environment near the mouth of a river. The co-occurrence of *Melanopsis gorgeixi broti* and *Theodoxus doricus fontannesi* proves the presence of fresh/brackish water. A possible explanation is that the site was a river bank. The sediments of the river could have buried the mollusc fauna and the coral remains. Most of the bivalves were found with closed valves, as there wasn't much time for the dispersal of the remains. There is strong evidence that the site is autochthonous as all *Panopea faujasi* were found in living position.

Figs. 3, 4: rich mollusc fauna in the layer.

Fig. 5: *Panopea faujasi*.

Fig. 6: broken bivalves.

Figs. 7-10: *Clausinella fasciata*, *Neverita josephinia*, *Trivia arctica*, *Calliostoma tauromiliare*.

Figs. 11-14: *Bolma rugosa*, *Gracilipurpura rostrata*, *Comarmondia gracilis*, *Chama placentina*.

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